

Understanding Personalized Informal Learning Environments: Towards Appreciating the Role of Technology Enhanced Informal Learning in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

Advances in technology access allow learners to mould their learning to their personal interests via the creation of informal personal learning environments (PLE's), using and adapting every day digital technologies. A comprehensive understanding of how learning is self-regulated within these PLE's and how they contribute to the acquisition and development of learners' digital literacy (DL) and self-regulated learning (SRL) skills is needed. Based on existing literature on the Viable System Model (VSM) of a learner within a PLE and DL, SRL constructs, a conceptual model is developed of the influences the development and use of a PLE has on the DL and SRL skills of students, as well as the interrelationships between constructs. A longitudinal mixed methods research approach is used to obtain quantitative and qualitative data. Structured equation modelling and thematic analysis is to be used for data analysis in order to investigate the interrelationships between constructs, as well as understand, and describe the use of informal PLE's for self-regulated learning. Our expected contribution is to create a more precise picture of the patterns and contexts of technology adoption by university students via empirical evidence. We aim to comprehend how they develop and foster DL skills via the informal use of technology within their PLE and the resultant impact on their SRL skills. We hope to provide broad insights on how undergraduates exploit and control the technological environment that surrounds them.

Keywords: *Personal Learning Environments, Digital Literacy, Self-Regulated Learning, Viable System Model*

INTRODUCTION

Customized informal personal learning environments (PLEs) are created by present day undergraduates as a learning strategy. These PLEs are comprised of a wide range of freely available tools and services accessible on ubiquitous digital devices. Components and content of such PLEs are changed to fit individual learning needs, rarely limiting to a single technology or even device.

PLE's support learners in defining their personal learning goals and autonomously managing their learning content, tools, and peers (Renzel, Klamma, Laanpere, & Nussbaumer, 2015). Being digitally literate (DL), by possessing a working knowledge of digital technology and understanding it's usage for learning is vital in such PLEs. This must be accompanied by strategies that promote, self-regulated learning (SRL), to remain attentive, motivated, and engaged in learning tasks (Azevedo, 2007).

The investigation of these user centred and customized PLEs have gained increasing interest. Empirical investigation, however, of informal PLEs and DL, SRL skill acquisition and interaction within them is still lacking. There is scope, particularly, for consideration of how the development and use of such PLEs

influence the digital and self-regulated learning skills of undergraduate students (Dabbagh & Kitsantas, 2012). Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify, understand and describe how undergraduate students are using and adapting everyday digital technologies for creating informal PLE's and the resultant impact on their DL and SRL skills.

We expect to augment knowledge of PLE's among Information Systems (IS) researchers by providing insight on how undergraduates develop and foster DL skills through the informal use of technology via their PLEs. Particularly, we attempt to clarify how self-regulated learning takes place and could vary as a result of interaction with technology for learning and digital skills developed herein. A further contribution to IS literature, is to create a more precise picture of the interrelationships between DL and SRL constructs within a PLE.

In the subsequent sections we discuss the research questions followed by a discussion of the research method to be employed in this study. The paper concludes with a discussion of the findings thus far, its expected contributions and directions for future research.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In this study the PLE is a concept recognized as a new approach to the use of digital technologies in learning. It is not linked to a particular technology, but defined as a practical intervention relating to the organization of all the different devices, tools and technologies undergraduates use in their everyday life for learning (Attwell, 2007 ; Gallego & Gamiz, 2015). These could include desktops, mobile devices (e.g. laptops, tablets, smartphones, PDAs), Web 2.0 tools and other collaborative resources on the internet as well as any open source or commercially available software packages. SRL, defined as self-generated thoughts, feelings, and actions that are planned and cyclically adapted to the attainment of personal learning goals (Zimmerman, 2000), precedes the dawn of the PLE in theory. SRL, however, is regarded as an essential characteristic of the PLE (Melzer & Schoop, 2015).

However, most prior studies on PLEs employ an experimental approach where a given technology is imposed on the students, and does not investigate how their current technological portfolio being used in daily life (i.e. everyday technologies) to create customised PLE's, could have or is having an impact on their SRL skills. The generalizability of the findings of studies conducted in the formal classroom to an informal PLE context is also limited. Furthermore, there is a lack of empirical evidence regarding how technology use influences SRL skills of students when learning within informal settings via the construction of their own PLEs. There is a need to comprehensively understand the SRL processes of students engaged in the use of these customised informal PLEs.

Moreover, PLEs are regarded as a context for developing DL skills (Laakkonen & Taalas, 2015). Eshet (2012), conceptualizes DL as referring to the collection of literacies associated with the usage of digital technologies. These multiple literacies are incorporated into technical, cognitive and social-emotional perspectives of online and offline learning with digital technologies (Ng, 2012). In Perera Muthupoltotage, Gardner, & Peiris (2016) , we provided the theoretical underpinnings for arguing that SRL capabilities of students, could have a positive influence on how well they apply DL skills for the learning task within a PLE and that DL skills could have a positive influence on the SRL skills of students.

Accordingly, the research questions for this study are:

RQ1. How are undergraduates using and adopting everyday technologies to perform self-regulated learning tasks within their informal PLE's?

RQ2. To what extent and in what ways are the digital literacy skills of students and their self-regulated learning skills interrelated when using an informal PLE?

METHODOLOGY

We adopt a mixed methods research approach for this study. It is deemed the most suitable to address our research questions which call for verification of hypothesis as well as real-life contextual understandings of the processes of learning with the aid of technology. An overview of data collection methods are depicted in table 1 below. The population used for the study will be Stage 1 students enrolled in courses in the Business School and Law faculty of a top university in the Asia-Pacific region.

Technique	Purpose	Sample
SURVEY1: Technology use and Digital Literacy Questionnaire - Web based	Self-report measure on frequency of technology use, level of usage, perception of usefulness, proficiency levels, digital skill development methods and scores for technical, cognitive and social emotional literacy based on Ng (2012)	A random sample of first year students
SURVEY2: Academic Self-Regulated Learning Questionnaire - Web based	Self-report measure of the level of SRL skills based on Magno (2010)	Consecutive sample of all respondents of the first survey, who indicated positive interest in further participation in data collection.
Face to face semi structured Interview and Mind map	Mind map to depict PLE Description of actual individual usage of PLE learning. Discuss past knowledge, opinions, conceptions and self-awareness of SRL and DL skills of the students within their PLE.	Judgmental convenience sample of respondents from the second survey.
Focus groups	Discuss the use of individual PLEs for learning specifically outside the classroom in a group setting. Focusing on SRL behavior and motivations.	A random sample of the interview participants.
Academic Performance Data from the university internal learner management system	Understand the manner in which current self-reported SRL skill levels reflect in student performance at learning tasks.	Assessment and performance related information on key technology related courses that they are enrolled in, for all the interviewed students.

Table 1: Data Collection Methods

The quantitative data collection and analysis to address the quantitative aspect of RQ2 is nearing completion. A two-wave longitudinal design was used to examine the reciprocal relationships among components of DL and SRL of university student. SPSS AMOS 18 was used for analysis of the data originating from the two surveys via Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) techniques in an attempt to validate our hypothesized bidirectional relationship between student's self-reported SRL skills and digital literacy. Detailed discussion of the survey instruments used, their validity, reliability (Perera Muthupoltotage & Gardner, in press) and findings of data analysis (Perera Muthupoltotage & Gardner, 2017) were reported.

Empirical analysis confirmed that a reciprocal model tested with 181 respondents fit the data well with significant predictive power. It was seen that technical literacy, which involves possessing the applicable technical and operational skills to employ digital technologies for learning, has a statistically significant positive reciprocal relationship with the SRL skills of students in our sample when controlled for age and gender. Social-emotional literacy, requires users to be highly critical and analytical, very mature, and have a good command of information, branching, and photo-visual literacy skills. This has been described as the highest-level and most complex of the digital literacy skills (Eshet, 2012). It too shows a significant positive reciprocal relationship with SRL when controlling for age and gender. While SRL does have a significant positive influence on subsequent cognitive literacy skills, this effect was not reciprocal for the sample studied. As all survey respondents were first year students of the business school and due to the more technological orientation of the courses they study this sample may be biased we are currently collecting data from a sample of Law school students to investigate any group differences.

The interviews and focus groups have been conducted and the data analysis is under way. The interviews enabled interviewees to voice their detailed opinions regarding their PLE use for learning, providing information about learners' experiences by enquiring on retrospective or prospective behavior. Before arriving, the interviewees were asked to complete a mind map of how they use technological tools and devices to learn (i.e their PLE). It was seen that initial completion of mind maps can aid in identifying unique concepts and providing more in-depth responses about their experience in subsequent interview. In the focus groups the participants were encouraged to provide descriptions of using their PLEs for informal learning tasks outside the classroom, and to describe in detail the self-regulation method they use in each situation.

We propose engaging in a thematic analysis of the interview and focus group data, to be coded and analyzed using NVIVO 11. The aim is to arrive at description and conceptualization of technology usage levels, perception of usefulness, proficiency levels, digital skill development methods and SRL strategies to help explain the interrelationship between DL and SRL skills of the participants within their PLEs. The PLE viable system model (PLE VSM) (Johnson & Liber, 2008), provides an apt theoretical starting point to clearly characterize how undergraduate learners can steer themselves in the present day complex technological domain. This model applies the Viable System Model (VSM) to the learner within a PLE and the activities needed to manage their learning, typically involving the self-regulatory actions the learner undertakes to make their different learning episodes comprehensible. It is of particular relevance to this study as it allows the identification of the dimensions of challenge to the viability of the learning process as well as ways of managing them. We propose to use this model to provide the theoretical underpinnings coding the interview and focus group data for answering RQ1 and the qualitative aspect of RQ2.

We also propose to obtain performance information for participants on key courses. This is done in order to obtain an insight in to how well these students perform academically, to enhance the richness of the data collected via the other techniques. This will provide a different facet to this investigation and enhance our understanding of the consequences of the SRL processes the students engage in, especially in light of arguments within literature that students with higher levels of SRL skills perform better from an academic perspective (Cheng, 2011).

EXPECTED CONTRIBUTIONS AND OUTLOOK

With our current study findings we can add further empirical validity and clarity to the claims that the use of technology impacts SRL skills, and show that SRL skills are influential in developing DL skills. The qualitative analysis which is presently underway would help in explaining and clarifying the above findings as well as identifying further factors which could influence this phenomena. We acknowledge that passive longitudinal designs of the manner we have adopted as most suitable for the context of this study, do not enable researchers to isolate independent variables and experimentally control potentially confounding variables. Our present findings, however, provide an opening for a comprehensive dialogue among researchers who are interested in understanding the patterns, contexts and consequences of technology adoption for learning in informal PLEs. Further, the measurement model we used in the quantitative analysis, could confirm that the DL and SRL constructs we used have appropriate reliability and validity and could encourage other researchers in incorporating these constructs in their research.

As we have not considered cultural attributes here, this research is ripe for replication in other cultural settings to determine if the relationships remain constant across different settings. The shortcomings of using self-report measures here could be mitigated by user observations in experiments, which could be applied in future research.

The theoretical contribution of our study is the holistic consideration of the interplay between DL and SRL, within PLEs to elaborate on its context and significance by applying a mixed-methods research approach. We believe that empirical evidence from this study would contribute towards creating a more precise picture of the patterns and contexts of technology adoption by university students, and the resultant impact on their SRL skills. It will specifically clarify the interplay between the DL skills of undergraduates and their SRL skills, how one may be influencing the other and vice versa, enriching the literature on both DL and SRL. On a more practical footing, deriving insights from our completed research, will enumerate the interaction between informal technology use and the transfer of relevant technological and learning skills to formal classroom use, contributing empirical evidence to the ongoing discussion of novel models of learning.

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